

RESTORATIVE JUSTICE APPROACH IN RESOLVING TRAFFIC ACCIDENT CASES THAT CAUSE SERIOUS INJURIES AND DEATH

BUDI SETIYONO

Doctoral Program in Law, Faculty of Law, Diponegoro University, Jl. Prof. Soedarto, SH., Tembalang, Semarang. Email: budisetiyono@students.undip.ac.id

YUSRIADI

Lecturer in Doctoral Law Program, Faculty of Law, Diponegoro University, Jl. Prof. Soedarto, SH., Tembalang, Semarang.

IRMA CAHYANINGTYAS

Lecturer in Doctoral Law Program, Faculty of Law, Diponegoro University, Jl. Prof. Soedarto, SH., Tembalang, Semarang.

Abstract

Justica's Restorative Approach in Solving Traffic Accident Cases that Cause Serious Injuries and Death. This study aims to examine; 1) What problems occur in the implementation of the implementation of *restorative* justice in the case of past laka resulting in death at this time? 2) Reconstruction of justice restoration policies in cases of past laka resulting in death based on the value of justice? The research method used is empirical juridical with a legal approach, concept approach, and case studies. The results showed that; 1) Various problems that occur in the implementation of the implementation of restorative justice in the case of past laka that result in death at this time due to several things including; a) legal factors; the absence of guidelines governing the limits of law enforcement discretion; b) Law Enforcement factors; Law Enforcement has difficulty handling cases due to the uncooperation of perpetrators and witnesses; c) means factors; limited facilities and infrastructure compared to Police Jurisdiction; d) Community legal awareness; ignorance of the public that the position of the peace letter does not invalidate the claim in Court; e) The legal culture of society; The public tends to shy away from Law Enforcement in resolving traffic accident disputes and fear being a witness in the event of an accident that causes someone to die. 2) Reconstruction of justice restoration policies in cases of past deaths resulting in justice values-based on justice can be carried out in several ways, including; a) legal factors; Creation of guidelines that regulate the limits of discretionary authority of law enforcement; b) Law Enforcement factors; Improve the ability, knowledge, and skills of law enforcement; c) means factors; improve facilities and infrastructure in accordance with Police Jurisdiction; d) Public legal awareness; increase public legal awareness that the position of the peace letter does not invalidate claims in Court; e) The legal culture of society; fostering a culture of community law that is orderly and cooperative with law enforcement

Keywords: Reconstruction, Policy, Restorative Justice, Accident, Traffic, Death.

INTRODUCTION

Background

The Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia is a state based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution. The Republic of Indonesia is a country based on law.¹ Indonesia adheres to the notion of the rule of law (*rechtstaat*), *not based on mere power* (*machstaat*).² This means that the Republic of Indonesia is a democratic state of law based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution. Indonesia is a country that aims to realize welfare for the

people (*welfare state*). This noble goal will be impossible to achieve without development in various fields of life as an absolute condition for achieving this state ideal as stated in the fourth paragraph of the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution.

The national development goals referred to in this case are not only limited to development in the physical field, but also include development in the legal field. Traffic law has the dual function of creating order and tranquility or freedom for all levels of society. Traffic laws must combine the freedom of road users with the order that society wants to achieve.

Such a situation must be combined with law enforcement by law enforcement so that the community feels safe, and the resolution of traffic cases will give birth to a sense of justice. Traffic problems are interesting, because traffic regulations are non-spiritual or neutral legal systems. Enforcing traffic rules is an arduous task. In traffic regulations, there are two tasks, namely maintaining public order and public peace. In addition, community members basically want freedom in using road facilities, while law enforcement is tasked with creating security and order.³

Often accidents that occur on the highway are actually the result of the negligence of the road users themselves. The accident that occurred was quite concerning because the victims were not only property but also lives. A person who commits negligence in driving a motor vehicle, especially one that results in another person losing his life (dies), makes peace with the victim's family. Even though there has been peace between the parties, criminal cases that cause other people to die continue as ordinary criminal cases.

Against these incidents, it often raises problems such as how the function of the peace letter made by the perpetrator of the crime with the family of the deceased. Also what are the legal consequences of the peace letter made by the perpetrator of the crime and the victim's family for the judge in deciding the case.

Every case of a traffic accident that occurs on the highway, of course, has legal consequences for the driver of the vehicle. Legal provisions governing fatal accidents that result in injury or death of a person, in general are the Criminal Code (Criminal Code) and specifically regulated in Law (Law) No. 22 of 2009 concerning Traffic. Often people view that traffic accidents that cause injuries and death, absolutely the fault is always on the driver of the vehicle concerned.

Meanwhile, according to the prevailing legal theory that a person's fault is seen from the actual incident factor, what factors cause the traffic accident. This can be revealed from the chronology of events, testimonies including eyewitnesses who saw the accident.

More specific laws and regulations regulate more specifically, in detail and firmly about traffic on highways / tolls and traffic accidents, including regulating negligence / negligence in driving vehicles to cause injury and death, namely Law Number 22 of 2009 concerning Road Traffic and Transportation ("Law LLAJ").

The pattern of solving social problems through alternative channels other than legal or non-litigation processes, among others, through peace efforts, is resolved through mediation, which is one form of the restorative justice approach. Mediation is a method that is often used by all parties involved in a traffic accident who eventually find consensus to resolve the case in a family way. Peace in criminal law in cases of traffic accidents often occurs and is applied by the people of Indonesia.

Problem Statement

1. What problems occur in the implementation of the implementation of restorative justice in the case of the current laka that resulted in death?
2. Reconstruction of justice restoration policies in cases of laka then resulting in death based on the value of justice?

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This research departs from the juridical implications of peace in the case of traffic accidents resulting in death to criminal prosecution and investigation. This is related to the criminal liability of perpetrators of traffic accidents that cause people to die. On the other hand, peace between the two parties has been carried out even though the peaceful settlement of criminal cases has no legal basis, either in the Criminal Procedure Code (Law No. 8 of 1981) or in other legislation.

Peace in the case of traffic accidents is mostly done by the community, although legally there is no basis. The only handle on the part of the investigator to do so is the willingness of the victim / exposed to the crime or his family to sign a peace letter so that the victim states that he will not hold charges for the signing event is that with the stamp of peace, the victim states that he will not hold charges for the events that occur, both criminally and civilly. The basis of this statement makes the investigator have a handle to stop the investigation. Although there is no legal handle, it turns out that adhering to a statement signed by the victim/victim's family, is quite effective in making the settlement of criminal cases outside the court peaceful, never a problem so that such practices still occur in practice.

Criminal acts come from a term in Dutch law, namely: *strafbaarfeit*. There are also those who term it to be *delict* which comes from Latin *Delictum*. Anglo Saxon penal code uses the term *offense* or *criminal act*. According to Moeljatno,⁴ Criminal acts are actions prohibited by a prohibition law which is accompanied by threats (sanctions) in the form of certain crimes, whoever violates the prohibition. The prohibition is aimed at the act, while the criminal threat is aimed at the person who caused the incident. Moeljatno separates between *criminal act* and *criminal responsibility* which is an element of a criminal act. According to Moeljatno are only the elements inherent in *criminal act* (punishable acts). Meanwhile, what includes the elements of a criminal act is an act that meets the formulation of the law is against the law.

Concrete law enforcement is the enactment of positive laws in practice as they should be obeyed. Therefore, providing justice in a case means deciding the law in concreto in maintaining and guaranteeing the observance of material law using procedural means established by formal law. The main theory used in this study is the Law Enforcement Theory which is supported by the theory of Justice. In relation to Law Enforcement Theory, it can be seen the role of the police in the application of *restorative justice* to traffic accidents in the old deli police station area in accordance with applicable laws and regulations.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is included in the type of collaborative research, where the approach method used is normative as well as empirical, namely normative juridical and empirical juridical collaboration. Normative legal research method, which is a study conducted by reviewing laws and regulations that apply or are applied to a particular legal problem. Normative research is often referred to as doctrinal research, which is research whose object of study is statutory documents and library materials.

This research uses various approaches, with the aim of obtaining information from various aspects of the issue under study. Therefore, to solve the problems that are the subject of discussion in this study, the following approaches are used: (1) Statute approach is an approach taken by reviewing laws and regulations related to the legal issue being raised.⁵ (2) The conceptual approach is an approach that departs from the views and doctrines that develop in the science of law.⁶ The case study approach is used with regard to legal cases that discuss community-based management of coastal and marine resources

The data source of a study is primary data and secondary data.⁷ Because this research is empirical and normative legal research, the sources studied are primary data sources, secondary data, and tertiary data.⁸ Primary legal materials are data that are materials in binding legal research sorted based on the hierarchy of legislation.⁹

The research technique in this study is descriptive analytical, where the analysis is carried out critically.¹⁰ The data collected in this study will be analyzed descriptively with a *qualitative approach*, namely by providing a thorough and in-depth explanation and explanation (*holistic / verstelen*).¹¹

RESEARCH RESULTS

Overview of Traffic Accidents

An accident is an unplanned and uncontrolled act, when the action and reaction of objects, materials, or radiation causes injury or possible injury. Traffic is the movement of vehicles, people and animals on the road. Motor Vehicles A motor vehicle is a vehicle driven by engineering equipment located on that vehicle. Traffic Accident A traffic accident is an unexpected and accidental road event involving a vehicle with or without other road users resulting in human casualties and/or property loss. Motorcycles A

motorcycle is a two-wheeled motor vehicle with or without houses and with or without side carriages or a three-wheeled motor vehicle without houses.

Classification of Traffic Accidents Based on Law Number 22 of 2009 concerning Traffic and Road Transportation, article 229 explains that the characteristics of traffic accidents can be divided into 3 (three) groups, namely:¹²

1. Minor Traffic Accidents, namely accidents that result in damage to vehicles and/or goods.
2. Moderate Traffic Accidents, which are accidents that result in minor injuries and damage to vehicles and/or goods.
3. Heavy Traffic Accidents, which are accidents that result in death or serious injury.

Definition of Traffic Literally the term traffic can be interpreted as the movement (back and forth) of humans or goods from one place to another using public road facilities. The definition of traffic is as follows: "traffic is walking back and forth, back and forth, regarding travel, and about transportation between one place and another (by shipping roads, air transportation, land and so on)". However, the definition of traffic in Law No. 22 of 2009 concerning Road Traffic and Transportation in article 1 point 2 is that traffic is the movement of vehicles and people in road traffic space, while what is meant by road traffic space is infrastructure that is demolished for the movement of vehicles, people, and / or goods in the form of roads and supporting facilities.

Road traffic violations are the most frequent traffic events. The violation in question is a violation of the prohibitions and obligations of the provisions in the field of traffic. Ramdlon Naning stated that what is meant by a traffic violation is the act or action of a person with the provisions of traffic laws and regulations. The violations referred to above are what are regulated in article 105 of Law No. 22 of 2009, namely: Everyone who uses the road must behave in an orderly manner; and/or prevent things that may hinder, endanger the security and safety of traffic and road transport, or that may cause road damage.

Thus, what is meant by traffic violations is the actions or actions of a person who is contrary to the provisions of traffic and road transportation laws and regulations and other laws and regulations¹³.

Accidents do not happen by chance, but there is a cause. Because there is a cause, the cause of the accident must be analyzed and found, so that corrective action to the cause can be taken and with further preventive efforts the accident can be prevented. An accident is an unplanned and uncontrolled act, when the action and reaction of objects, materials, or radiation causes injury or possible injury. An accident can be defined as any unplanned and controlled event that can be caused by humans, situations, environmental factors, or a combination of these things that interfere with the work process and can cause injury or not, pain, death, property damage or other unwanted events.

Based on Law Number 22 of 2009 concerning Road Traffic and Transportation, disclosing a traffic accident is an unexpected and accidental road event involving vehicles with or without other road users resulting in human casualties and/or property losses. A traffic accident is an event in road traffic involving at least one vehicle that causes injury or damage or loss to its owner (victim) (WHO, 1984). Traffic accidents are events that are difficult to predict when and where they occur.¹⁴

Accidents are not only trauma, injury, or disability but also death. Accident cases are difficult to minimize and tend to increase with the increase in road length and the number of movements from vehicles.

From several definitions of traffic accidents, it can be concluded that a traffic accident is an event in road traffic that is unexpected and undesirable that is difficult to predict when and where it occurs, involving at least one vehicle with or without other road users that causes injury, trauma, disability, death and/or property loss to its owner (victim).¹⁵

Traffic accidents are a serious problem in Indonesia. Viewed from a macroeconomic perspective, accidents are inefficiencies in the implementation of transportation or a loss that reduces the quantity and quality of people and goods transported including increasing the totality of transportation costs. Accidents do not occur by chance, but are caused by several factors that cause accidents that must be analyzed so that corrective actions and preventive efforts (prevention) of traffic accidents can be carried out. Traffic accidents claim the lives of about 1.2 million people every year according to WHO. In this regard, various programs for handling road traffic accidents have been implemented by various agencies, both government and private.¹⁶

Based on Law Number 22 of 2009 states that a traffic accident is an unexpected and accidental road event caused by vehicles with or without other road users resulting in human casualties and/or property losses. Traffic accidents are events in road traffic caused by at least one vehicle causing injury, damage, or loss to its owner or victim (WHO, 1984).

Technically, a traffic accident is defined as an event caused by many factors that accidentally occur (*Random Multy Factor Event*). In a simple sense, that a traffic accident occurs when all factors of the situation simultaneously at one particular point in time coincide with occurring. This means that it is difficult to predict exactly where and when an accident will occur.¹⁷

Overview of Justice

Restorative Justice

Restorative *Justice* is a term that has been known in Indonesian law since the 1960s as one of the stages in the conventional criminal justice system. Initially, Restorative Justice is a concept of case resolution that has been used by indigenous peoples in Indonesia as a method of solving cases that occur within the indigenous community concerned without involving state officials.

Miriam Liebman defines Restorative Justice as: "*Restorative justice has become the term generally used for an approach to criminal justice (and other justice systems such as a school disciplinary system) that emphasizes restoring the victim and community rather than punishing the offender*" (Restorative justice has become a commonly used term in the penal approach (as a penal system such as a disciplinary school system) that emphasizes the concept of putting the victim and environment back in their original state rather than punishing the perpetrator of the crime.)¹⁸

The concept of Restorative Justice emphasizes a justice based on peace which in solving a case does not recognize justice based on revenge or punishment of perpetrators. The application of this concept is a form of development in the criminal justice system that focuses on the involvement between perpetrators and victims in solving a case where it is not one of the mechanisms known in conventional criminal procedural law today.

Van Ness, as quoted by Mudzakkir, says that Restorative Justice is characterized by several prepositions, namely:¹⁹ 1. Crime is a conflict between individuals that results in harm to the victim, society and the perpetrator himself. 2. The goal to be achieved of the criminal justice process is to reconcile between the parties while remedying the harm caused by the crime. 3. The criminal justice process should facilitate the active participation of victims, offenders and the public. Criminal justice should not be dominated by the state to the exclusion of everything else.

The Restorative Justice approach in solving a crime provides an opportunity for the parties involved, especially perpetrators and victims, to participate in the resolution of cases so that there is a transfer of functions of perpetrators and victims where in conventional criminal procedural law, perpetrators and victims only function as witnesses in solving cases carried out by law enforcement officials. This perspective has created a renewal in the resolution of a case that imposing a crime against a perpetrator who is legally considered guilty of a criminal act does not guarantee the fulfillment of the interests of the victim and has a deterrent effect on the perpetrator. However, deliberation between perpetrators and victims applied in restorative justice can certainly achieve this, that between perpetrators and victims will choose a form of case resolution that meets the interests of both where restorative justice seeks to emphasize the responsibility of the perpetrator for his behavior that causes harm to others.²⁰

In principle, Restorative *Justice seeks* peace outside the court involving the perpetrator of a criminal act (his family) against the victim. In Restorative Justice, the resolution of a legal problem that occurs between the perpetrator and the victim of a criminal act can be achieved if there is an agreement or agreement between the parties so as to provide an opportunity for the perpetrator to be responsible for all his actions by compensating for losses due to the criminal act he committed.²¹

Legal Regulation for Solving Traffic Accident Cases that Cause Death through a Restorative Justice Approach

Restorative justice as a concept is a new thing in the criminal law system in Indonesia. However, at the level of restorative justice practice, it has long been known and also practiced by indigenous peoples of Indonesia through the implementation of customary law systems by various kinds of indigenous peoples of Indonesia. Such as the indigenous peoples of Papua, Toraja, Minangkabau, Kalimantan, Central Java and other indigenous communities that still hold strong culture. The Indonesian state that makes Pancasila the basis of the state (philosophical nation), in such a position, then Pancasila is the highest norm in the legal structure whose position is higher than the constitution or Basic Law.²²

The basic values contained in Pancasila actually have the concept of *restorative justice* long before this idea was present and entered the juvenile criminal justice system. This can be seen in the formulation of the 4th Precept of Pancasila, which states that "peoplehood is led by wisdom in representative consultations." Looking at the formulation of the 4th Precept of Pancasila, it means that the Indonesian nation has long glorified the principle of deliberation as a habit in solving every problem that occurs in society, including overcoming national problems on a national scale.²³

Deliberation and consensus, in the context of restorative justice, can be carried out in various ways, including mediation, compensation, or other methods agreed between victims and perpetrators. Other parties can be involved in the settlement process as mediators, if it turns out that no agreement is reached between the victim and the perpetrator, then the matter is processed through court channels (litigation). Deliberation and consensus contained in the 4th Precept of Pancasila is a concept of problem resolution or dispute that aims to create a balance between the parties to the dispute, so that the problem can be resolved by reaching an agreement by accommodating the interests of the parties to the dispute.

Settlement in this way will certainly be better able to fulfill and provide justice for all parties, which is the ultimate goal of the Pancasila state legal system. This is in accordance with the basic values contained in the 5th Precept of Pancasila, which means that the life of the nation and state, is based on "social justice for all Indonesian people".

Historically, *restorative justice* has been inspired by "*community justice*" which is still used in some cultures of non-Western societies, especially *indigenous populations*. Its development, *restorative justice* is much influenced by thoughts about equality and public relations. Although the idea or idea of restorative justice *does not come from the culture of Indonesian society*, restorative justice patterns are *embedded in several traditions of indigenous peoples in Indonesia*.²⁴

The compatibility of *restorative justice with the basic values of Pancasila as proof that restorative justice has long been known and practiced by the Indonesian people*. However, as an instrument in criminal law enforcement, the application of restorative justice is a new thing, especially in the criminal law system. *Restorative Justice* began to

be known and applied in the Indonesian legal system after the issuance of Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System which specifies that the resolution of child cases facing the law is carried out through a *restorative justice approach*. Positive law stipulates that criminal cases cannot be resolved outside the court process, but in certain cases it is possible to carry it out. In practice criminal law enforcement in Indonesia, although there is no formal legal basis, criminal cases are often resolved outside the court process through the discretion of law enforcement officials, peace mechanisms, customary institutions and so on.

The existence of *restorative justice* in the criminal justice system can be said to be between "existing" and "nothing". That being said, on the one hand because *restorative justice* in the provisions of the law is not known in the Criminal Justice System, but at the level under the law it is known in a limited way through the discretion of law enforcement and is partial. Then, on the other hand, it turns out that the practice of restorative justice has been carried out by the Indonesian people and the settlement is carried out outside the court such as through the mechanism of customary institutions.²⁵

Based on the description above, it can be understood that *restorative justice* has not been integrated in the criminal justice system. However, along with the reforms in criminal law and criminal procedural law, the concept of restorative justice began to be applied in solving criminal cases in certain cases, such as for minor crimes. The resolution of criminal acts through a *restorative justice* approach is explicitly regulated in Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System. The *restorative justice approach* is carried out through diversion at each level through the mediation process. Article 1 paragraph (7) of Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Juvenile Criminal Justice System, states that diversion is a transfer of the resolution of child cases from the criminal justice process to processes outside criminal justice. Diversion is carried out for 30 days to reach an agreement between the two parties.²⁶

Juridically, the legal provisions that are the basis for investigators of the Laka Lantas Polres Batubara in applying *restorative justice* in solving traffic accident cases refer to the provisions of Article 18 paragraph (1) of Law Number 2 of 2002 concerning the National Police of the Republic of Indonesia (called the National Police Law), which states: "In the public interest officials of the National Police of the Republic of Indonesia in carrying out their duties and authorities may act according to his own judgment".

According to the provisions of Article 230 of the LLAJ Law, that: "every traffic accident case that meets the criminal elements must be resolved through the criminal justice process". This means that the police must carry out / take legal action, while the legal action in question is to investigate every report of traffic accident victims and at the same time delegate the case that has been completed to the Prosecutor's Office.²⁷

In practice, police investigators in receiving reports of victims of traffic accidents do not necessarily take legal action as mentioned in Article 230 of the LLAJ Law. In certain circumstances, police investigators often resolve traffic accident cases through a

restorative justice approach or penal mediation. Thus, the ideal role that police investigators should perform is not carried out in accordance with the sound of the law. This is where investigator Laka then uses his discretionary authority in responding to and solving traffic accident cases as stipulated in Article 18 of the LLAJ Law.

Another legal basis that is the basis for traffic police investigators to apply penal mediation in solving criminal cases is referring to the Letter of the Chief of Police Pol Number: B/3022/XII/2009/SDEOPS, dated December 14, 2009 concerning Case Handling Through *Alternative Dispute Resolution* (ADR). The principle of penal mediation referred to in the Letter of the Chief of Police emphasizes that the settlement of criminal cases using ADR can only be carried out if there is agreement from the parties, both victims and suspects or parties to the dispute, but if there is no agreement, it is still resolved in accordance with applicable legal procedures. Furthermore, the discretion of the laka investigator is also seen in the application of Article 63 paragraph (3) of Perkap Number 15 of 2013 concerning Procedures for Handling Traffic Accidents. In the provisions of Article 63 paragraph (3) of Perkap Number 15 of 2013, it is determined that: "The settlement of cases outside the court as referred to in paragraph (2) can be carried out as long as a police report has not been made". This provision provides an opportunity for police investigators in the laka unit to take discretionary actions in solving traffic accident cases through penal mediation.²⁸

The settlement of traffic accident cases through a *restorative justice* approach by settling cases outside the court (penal mediation) is basically the exercise of discretionary authority exercised by the police as mentioned in Article 18 paragraph (1) of the Police Law. However, in the context of Indonesia as a state of law, discretionary actions taken by law enforcement officials must also be legally accountable. In response to this, police leaders often look for the right legal basis to legalize the termination of cases in the public interest, which includes pure delicacies.

In accordance with the Secret Telegram Number STR/583/VIII/2012 concerning the application of *Restorative Justice* from Kabareskrim to the Para-Dir Reskrim, Dir Reskrimsus, and Dir Resobat in all Polda in the Republic of Indonesia, related to the exercise of police authority to take or take action on self-assessment based on consideration of the benefits and risks of such actions and really in the public interest as regulated and mentioned in Article 18 of the Police Act.

In its development, the Chief of Police also issued a Circular Letter of the Chief of Police Number 8 of 2018 concerning the Application of *Restorative Justice* in the Settlement of Criminal Cases. This circular letter of the Chief of Police on *Restorative Justice* is further used as a legal basis and guideline for investigators and investigators of the National Police who carry out investigations / investigations, including as a guarantee of legal protection and control supervision, in the application of the principles of *restorative justice* in the concept of investigation and investigation of criminal acts in order to realize the public interest and a sense of community justice, so as to realize uniformity in understanding and application of restorative justice in the National Police Environment.

Then in terms of stopping the investigation, to create uniformity in the implementation of the termination and become a guideline for the police in carrying out the termination, the Chief of Police also issued a Circular Letter of the Chief of Police Number 7 of 2018 concerning Termination of Investigation. Based on the description above, it can be understood that the legal basis for the implementation of restorative justice in resolving traffic accident cases through out-of-court case settlement (penal mediation) is based on the discretionary authority possessed by the police. Police discretion occurs when a police officer is faced with decision-making when there are various options for action. Meanwhile, what is meant by police discretion in investigating criminal acts is discretion carried out by investigators at the technical level of investigation or ignoring the technical level of investigation while still paying attention to procedures and laws and regulations, which aim to maintain public security and order.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion, several things can be concluded as follows:

1. Various problems that occur in the implementation of the implementation of *restorative justice in* the case of past laka that result in death at this time due to several things include; a) legal factors; the absence of guidelines governing the limits of law enforcement discretion; b) Law Enforcement factors; Law Enforcement has difficulty handling cases due to the uncooperation of perpetrators and witnesses; c) means factors; limited facilities and infrastructure compared to Police Jurisdiction; d) Community legal awareness; ignorance of the public that the position of the peace letter does not invalidate the claim in Court; e) The legal culture of society; The public tends to shy away from Law Enforcement in resolving traffic accident disputes and fear being a witness in the event of an accident that causes someone to die.
2. Reconstruction of justice restoration policies in cases of past deaths based on justice values can be carried out in several ways, including; a) legal factors; Creation of guidelines that regulate the limits of discretionary authority of law enforcement; b) Law Enforcement factors; Improve the ability, knowledge, and skills of law enforcement; c) means factors; improve facilities and infrastructure in accordance with Police Jurisdiction; d) Public legal awareness; increase public legal awareness that the position of the peace letter does not invalidate claims in Court; e) The legal culture of society; Fostering a culture of community law that is orderly and cooperative with law enforcement.

Footnotes

- 1) Article 1 paragraph (3) of the Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia Year 1945
- 2) Jimly Ashidiqie, Commentary on the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, Sinar Grafika, Jakarta, 2009. p. 12
- 3) Soerjono Soekanto, Legal Awareness and Legal Compliance, Rajawali, Jakarta, 1982, p. 56

- 4) Moeljatno, Principles of Criminal Law. Renika Cipta. Prints 8. Jakarta, 2009, p.165
- 5) Johnny Ibrahim, Theory and Methodology of Normative Legal Research (Malang: Banyumedia Publishing, 2006), p. 101.
- 6) Peter Mahmud Marzuki, Legal Research (Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Group, 2008).
- 7) Mahmud Marzuki and Peter Mahmud, "Legal Research," Journal of Legal Research (Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Group, 2011), p. 25.
- 8) Soekanto and Mamudji, Normative Legal Research, A Brief Review.
- 9) Marzuki, Legal Research.
- 10) Satjipto Rahardjo, The Science of Law: The Search, Liberation and Enlightenment. (Semarang: Diponegoro University, 2003).
- 11) Sugiyono, "Quantitative, Qualitative and R&D Research Methods," 26th (Bandung: Cv. Alfabeta, 2018), p. 34.
- 12) Soedjono Dirdjosisworo. Socio-criminology Practice of Social Sciences in the Study of Crime. Bandung: Sinar Baru, 1984, p 51.
- 13) Harun M.Husen, Crime and Law Enforcement in Indonesia, Jakarta, Rineka Cipta, 1990, p. 58
- 14) Desy Anwar, Complete Dictionary Indonesian. Surabaya: Amelia. 2003, p. 45.
- 15) Bambang Poernomo, Legal Growth of Deviations Beyond the Codification of Criminal Law, Bina Aksara, Jakarta, 1984. p, 10.
- 16) Ibid. p. 46.
- 17) A.Z. Abidin, Potpourri of Criminal Law, Pradnya Paramita, Jakarta, 1993, p. 33.
- 18) Miriam Liebman, Restorative justice: How It Works, Jessica Kingsley Publishers, London, 2007, p. 27.
- 19) G. Widiartana and Aloysius Wisnubroto, Reform of Criminal Procedure Law", Citra Aditya Bakti, Bandung, 2005, p. 42
- 20) H. Siswanto Sunarso, Victimology in the Criminal Justice System, Sinar Grafika, Jakarta, 2014, p. 157.
- 21) Zevanya Simanungkalit, Thesis: "Legal Analysis of the Application of Restorative Justice in Traffic Accidents" (Makassar: UNHAS, 2016), p. 16.
- 22) Teguh Prasetyo and Arie Purnomosidi, Building Law Based on Pancasila, Bandung; Nusa Media, 2014, p. 41
- 23) Mary Ellen Reimund, "Mediation in Criminal Justice: A Restorative Approach" Advocate, No. 46, 2003, p. 22
- 24) Jonlar Purba, Law Enforcement Against Lightly Motivated Crimes with Restorative Justice, Jakarta; Gem Literacy, 2017, p. 61
- 25) Lilik Mulyadi. Penal mediation in the criminal justice system. Jurnal Pro Yustitia Vol. 2 No. 1 January-April 2013, p. 3.
- 26) Gabriel H. Teninbaum, "Easing the Burden: Mediating Misdemeanor criminal Matters", Dispute ResolutionJournal, No. 62, 2007, p. 74
- 27) Roeslan Saleh, An orientation in criminal law, Aksara Baru, Jakarta, 1978, p.8
- 28) Randy Pradityo, "Restorative Justice in the Juvenile Criminal Justice System" Journal of Law and Justice, vol. 5 No. 3, 2016, p. 325.

Bibliography

1. Z. Abidin, *Potpourri of Criminal Law*, Pradnya Paramita, Jakarta, 1993
- 2) Bambang Poernomo, *Legal Growth of Deviations Beyond the Codification of Criminal Law*, Bina Aksara, Jakarta, 1984.
- 3) Desy Anwar, *Complete Dictionary Indonesian*. Surabaya: Amelia. 2003.
- 4) Gabriel H. Teninbaum, "Easing the Burden: Mediating Misdemeanor Criminal Matters", *Dispute Resolution Journal*, No. 62, 2007.
- 5) G. Widiartana and Aloysius Wisnubroto, *Reform of Criminal Procedure Law*", Citra Aditya Bakti, Bandung, 2005.
- 6) Harun M.Husen, *Crime and Law Enforcement in Indonesia*, Jakarta, Rineka Cipta, 1990
- 7) H. Siswanto Sunarso, *Victimology in the Criminal Justice System*, Sinar Grafika, Jakarta, 2014.
- 8) Jack B. Weinstein, "Some Benefit and Risks of Privatization of Justice Though ADR", *Ohio State Journal on Dispute Resolution*, 1996.
- 9) Jimly Ashidique, *Commentary on the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia*, Sinar Grafika, Jakarta, 2009.
- 10) Johnny Ibrahim, *Theory and Methodology of Normative Legal Research*. Malang: Banyumedia Publishing, 2006.
- 11) Jonlar Purba, *Law Enforcement Against Lightly Motivated Crimes with Restorative Justice*, Jakarta; Gem Literacy, 2017.
- 12) Mahmud Marzuki and Peter Mahmud, "Legal Research," *Journal of Legal Research*. Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Group, 2011.
- 13) Mary Ellen Reimund, "Mediation in Criminal Justice: A Restorative Approach" *Advocate*, no. 46. 2003.
- 14) Miriam Liebman, *Restorative justice: How It Works*, Jessica Kingsley Publishers, London, 2007.
- 15) Moeljatno, *Principles of Criminal Law*. Renika Cipta. Prints 8. Jakarta, 2009.
- 16) Article 1 paragraph (3) of the Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia Year 1945
- 17) Peter Mahmud Marzuki, *Legal Research*. Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Group, 2008.
- 18) Randy Pradityo, "Restorative Justice in the Juvenile Criminal Justice System" *Journal of Law and Justice*, vol. 5 No. 3, 2016.
- 19) Roeslan Saleh, *An orientation in criminal law*, Aksara Baru, Jakarta, 1978.
- 20) Satjipto Rahardjo, *The Science of Law: The Search, Liberation and Enlightenment*. Semarang: Diponegoro University, 2003.
- 21) Soerjono Soekanto, *Legal Awareness and Legal Compliance*, Rajawali, Jakarta, 1982.
- 22) Soekanto and Mamudji, *Normative Legal Research, A Brief Review*.
- 23) S. Nasution and M. Thomas, *Guidebook for Making Thesis, Thesis, Dissertation and Papers*, Jemmars, Bandung, 1988.
- 24) Sugiyono, "Quantitative, Qualitative and R&D Research Methods," *26th* (Bandung: Cv. Alfabeta, 2018).

- 25) Soedjono Dirdjosisworo. *Socio-criminology Practice of Social Sciences in the Study of Crime*. Bandung: Sinar Baru, 1984.
- 26) Teguh Prasetyo and Arie Purnomosidi, *Building Law Based on Pancasila*, Bandung; Nusa Media, 2014.
- 27) Zevanya Simanungkalit, Thesis: "Legal Analysis of the Application of Restorative Justice in Traffic Accidents" (Makassar: UNHAS, 2016).